

Fig 1(c). Plot of $\log i/i_d - i$ vs $-E_d e.$ at different temperatures for Th_4^+ -DOH system.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF i_d , $E_{1/2}$, αn AND $K_{f,h}^0$ FOR Th^{4+} -DOH SYSTEM AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES [Fig. 1(c)]

Temperature (°C)	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$	Temperature coefficient (percent per deg)	$D_0 \times 10^6$	αn	$K_{f,h}^0$ cm/sec
25	1.3	1.285	—	5.193	0.7526	6.148×10^{-17}
30	1.5	1.280	2.865	6.915	0.8130	7.109×10^{-18}
35	1.7	1.270	2.683	8.880	0.9173	1.927×10^{-19}

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Kinetics of Oxidation of Substituted Benzaldehydes by KMnO_4 in Buffer Medium

P. RAGHUNATHA RAO and E. V. SUNDARAM

Department of Chemistry, Kakatiya University, Warangal-506 009

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In our earlier paper¹ we reported on the kinetics of oxidation of *p*-nitro benzaldehydes by permanganate. We have extended the work on kinetics of

oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by permanganate in buffer medium to various substituted benzaldehydes namely *o*-Cl, *o*-CH₃, *o*-NO₂, *m*-CH₃, *m*-NO₂, 2,4-dichloro, 2,6-dichloro and 2,4-dinitro. An attempt has also been made to verify the general acid catalysis, relative rate of buffer activity with the same substrate, substituent effect, order of reactivity for isomeric benzaldehydes, evaluation of kinetic parameters, steric effects and quantitative calculation of steric interaction energies.

Results and Discussion

Wiberg^{2,3} studied oxidation of aromatic aldehydes by KMnO_4 in neutral medium and proposed a mechanism. In order to verify the general acid catalysis for the above aldehydes, experiments were carried out at constant pH, temperature and ionic strength but at different concentrations of buffer. The buffers selected were pyrophosphate, dihydrogen phosphate and acetate. Other buffers could not be used as they were oxidised by permanganate. The second order rate constants as a function of buffer concentrations are given in Table 1 for *ortho*-nitro compound in three buffers as an example. It was found that increase in buffer concentration increased the rate of reaction for all substrates in three buffers. This confirms that the title reaction undergoes general acid catalysis. To find out the relative rate of buffer activity experiments were done with the same substrate in different buffers under similar conditions. The results given in Table 1 show that the relative rate of buffer activity was found to be pyrophosphate > dihydrogen phosphate > acetate.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF BUFFER CONCENTRATION ON RATE CONSTANT IN PERMANGANATE-*o*-NO₂ BENZALDEHYDE REACTION

$[\text{RCHO}]_0 = 4.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$; $[\text{MnO}_4^-]_0 = 5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$; pH=6.5; $\mu = 0.2 \text{ M}$; Temp.=35°

$[\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^-]$	k_2	$[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4^-]$	k_2	$[\text{P}_2\text{O}_7^{4-}]$	k_2
0.20	0.20	0.20	0.28	0.020	0.25
0.15	0.18	0.15	0.24	0.015	0.22
0.10	0.16	0.10	0.19	0.010	0.19
0.05	0.11	0.05	0.15	0.005	0.14
0.01	0.08	0.01	0.10	0.0025	0.12

Units of $k_2 = 1. \text{m}^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1}$.

The substituent effect on the reaction was studied at constant pH, temperature, and buffer concentration for the above substituted benzaldehydes and the rate constants are given in Table 2. The following substituent effect was observed in dihydrogen phosphate buffer of 0.01 M at 25° when pH is 6.5.

$p\text{-NO}_2 > m\text{-NO}_2 > \text{H} > p\text{-CH}_3 > m\text{-CH}_3 > o\text{-NO}_2 > m\text{-Cl} > o\text{-Cl} > o\text{-CH}_3$. It was found from the substituent effect that electron withdrawing substituents enhance the rate of reaction while electron donating substituents reduce it. The order of reactivity for a given isomeric benzaldehydes was *para* > *meta* > *ortho*. This shows that *ortho* compounds are slower

TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANTS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE OXIDATION OF SUBSTITUTED BENZALDEHYDES BY PERMANGANATE IN $H_2PO_4^-$ BUFFER AT 35°

Substituent	k_2 l.mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ K. cal/mole	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ Cals/degree
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	0.302	6.72	39.3
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	0.261	9.01	32.1
<i>m</i> -CH ₃	0.108	11.04	25.8
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	0.125	10.44	31.0
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	0.104	12.22	23.0
<i>m</i> -Cl	0.088	8.54	35.9
<i>o</i> -Cl	0.081	6.72	41.8
2,6-Cl ₂	0.062	7.17	40.9
<i>o</i> -CH ₃	0.067	8.53	36.5
2,4-Cl ₂	0.032	5.15	49.1
2,4-(NO ₂) ₂	0.107	10.40	29.8
<i>n</i> -H	0.224	—	—

* Values taken from reference 2.

in oxidation than *para* ones. In other words steric effect of substituent near the reaction centre retards the rate of reaction. The lower kinetic rate observed for *ortho* isomer compared to *para* isomer is due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding leading to formation of a stable five or six membered ring. The other reason for *ortho* compounds reacting at a lower rate compared to *para* or *meta* isomers may be the presence of the bulky group near the reaction site. In case of *o*-nitro benzaldehyde intramolecular hydrogen bonding leads to the formation of a six membered ring whereas with *o*-chloro compound a five membered ring may be formed which is usually stable. This makes it difficult for C-H bond to break and hence the lower kinetic rate in the case of *ortho* compounds. In case of *o*-methyl, the bulky nature of substituent retards the rate. The same effect was also confirmed using 2,6-dichloro compound which is much slower than the *o*-chloro compound. The rate constant for unsubstituted, *o*-chloro and 2,6-dichloro benzaldehyde in dihydrogen phosphate buffer at 25° are 0.224, 0.040 and 0.024 l.m⁻¹ sec⁻¹, respectively. This type of steric effect retarding the rate of reaction was observed by Jayaraman* in the oxidation of benzaldehydes by Cr(VI).

The oxidation was studied in the temperature range from 30 to 50° for all aldehydes in 0.01 M dihydrogen phosphate buffer at pH 6.5. The second order rate constants at 35° and kinetic parameters are given in Table 2. The free energy of activation is of the order 19.6 K. cal/mole for all substituents. A linear isokinetic plot of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ against $\Delta S^\ddagger$ shows that all substituted benzaldehydes undergo the same type of mechanism in the buffer medium. The isokinetic temperature was calculated as 275°K from the isokinetic plot.

Evaluation of steric effects: The steric effects due to *ortho* substituents have been evaluated using the linear steric energy relationship⁶

$$\log(k_{ortho}/k_{unsub}) = \delta E_s$$

where δ is reaction constant, giving the susceptibility of a reaction series to steric effects of substituents. δ depends only upon the nature of the

reaction series and is independent of the substituent groups. E_s is steric substituent constant. $\log(k_{ortho}/k_{unsub})$ measures nearly quantitatively the total steric effect of a given substituent relative to the standard substituent, namely methyl group or unsubstituted compound. The positive δ values indicate that the steric requirements of substituents are greater in the transition state than in the initial state.

The negative δ values showed that the substituents of increasing size cause rates to be facilitated as a result of greater steric requirements of the substituents in the reactant than in the transition state.

The steric interaction energy⁶ has been calculated using the expression^{7,8} $\Delta(\Delta G_s) = -2.303 RT(\delta E_s)$. The values of δE_s and $\Delta(\Delta G_s)$ are given in Table 3 for *o*-NO₂, *o*-Cl and *o*-CH₃ benzaldehydes in buffer medium. All the *ortho* compounds are slower in

TABLE 3—VALUES OF RATE CONSTANTS (k_2), δE_s AND $\Delta(\Delta G_s)$ FOR *ortho* COMPOUNDS IN PERMANGANATE OXIDATION

Property	-NO ₂	-Cl	-CH ₃
k_2 l.m ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	0.05	0.04	0.038
δE_s	-0.51	-0.61	-0.72
$\Delta(\Delta G_s)$ (K.cals/mole)	0.69	0.83	0.98

rate than unsubstituted because of steric effect of substituent near the reaction centre. As is seen from results in Table 3, the values of δE_s decrease as one proceeds from nitro, chloro to methyl indicating that rate constants should decrease in that order. Similarly, it is seen that the $\Delta(\Delta G_s)$ values are increasing suggesting that the rate constants should decrease in that order. This can be seen from Table 3, where the rate constants for *o*-NO₂, *o*-Cl and *o*-CH₃ are given.

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